

Effects of Guided Discovery Teaching Method on Basic Science Students' Achievement in Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

IDOLLO, Ejiro¹ and Prof. KPANGBAN, Emperor²

^{1&2}Department of Science Education

Faculty of Education

Delta State University, Abraka.

¹ejaro4real@gmail.com

²professorkpangban@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined the effects of guided discovery teaching method on Basic Science students' achievement in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The study employed a Pre-test, Post-test, Non-Equivalent control group, Quasi-experimental design. The total population of the study was six thousand, eight hundred and two (6,802) which consist of all junior secondary school Basic science students in Delta North Senatorial District. The sample of the study is made up of 228 (107 for experimental group and 121 for control group) Basic science students sampled from four (4) local government areas using four (4) schools in the senatorial district, using random sampling technique. Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) was used for data collection. BSAT has a reliability coefficient value of 0.77 obtained using Kuder Richardson formula (21). The data obtained was analyzed using mean, standard deviation, t-test and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The result of the study showed that: students taught Basic Science using guided discovery performed significantly better than their counterparts taught with lecture method. Additionally, the study concludes that there was no statistically significant interaction effect between instructional method and sex of students taught using guided discovery and the lecture method. The study recommends amongst others that educational authorities and school administrators should integrate the guided discovery teaching method into the Basic Science curriculum, ensuring that teachers are trained to effectively utilize this approach to enhance students learning outcome.

Keywords: Basic Science Students, Guided Discovery Teaching method, Lecture method, Achievement, Sex.

Introduction

Teaching is one of the major concerns of every educational system. It is the practice implemented by a teacher aimed at transmitting skills (knowledge, know-how and internal-personal skills) to a learner, a student or any other audience in the context of an educational system. Ekiugbo (2024) defined teaching in terms of intention of producing learning. A classroom teacher is, therefore, a person who has undergone the required professional training in education, at the appropriate levels, capable of imparting skills, attitude and knowledge to the learners. According to Agunbiade (2019) every teaching must have a definite purpose of embracing the teacher and the

student's factor. The teacher influences the students' behavior and the students in turn, intentionally learn new values, skills, attitudes or knowledge.

Education plays a vital role in Nation building through the acquisition and transmission of knowledge and with this in mind, the Nigerian government in its National Policy on Education, 2013 place emphasis on science and technology for the actualization of this National development and thus, Basic science has been made mandatory as a subject for all Nigerian children at the Basic Education level, this is because:

1. Basic science concepts are organized sequentially into themes which helps arouse curiosity, develop scientific attitudes, reflective thinking and good habits in learners (Agogo and Ode, 2011).
2. It is a unified science with a holistic approach that presents science in a simplified manner to learners and hence increase their interest in learning of science.
3. It is a foundational science that prepares the child in the learning of other science-related courses.
4. It helps learner acquire the specific science process skills such as observing, organizing information, measuring, generalizing, predicting and designing experiments to check predictions (FRN, 2013).

The Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2008) core-curriculum for Basic Science from JSS I – JSS III emphasized the need for planned learning experience to be child centered. The design of the core-curriculum of Basic Science also includes some basic assumptions. These assumptions are, that: The pupil entering the junior secondary school programme had no prior knowledge of science. The basic professional qualification for those who will teach the course will be the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). With reference to the National Policy on Education FME (2008), the teaching of Basic Science from the pre-secondary through the Junior Secondary School levels is intended to achieve the following aims: Firstly, to inculcate in the learners, the spirit of inquiry and creativity through exploration of nature and local environment. Secondly, to lay sound basis for scientific innovation and reflective thinking. Thirdly, to develop in the child the ability to adapt to his/her changing environment. Fourthly, to give the child opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable the child to function effectively in the society within the limits of his/her capacity.

One teaching method that is student-centered and may help actualize the above aims and objectives is the Guided discovery teaching method. Guided discovery teaching method is a student-centered instructional approach in which the teacher acts as a facilitator, guiding students through the process of inquiry and discovery (Oludipe, 2011). This method encourages students to actively engage with the material, think critically, and develop problem-solving skills. The guided discovery teaching method is often used in the teaching of basic science subjects, such as biology, chemistry, and physics, to help students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.

In spite of its importance, there has been poor achievement in the subject both in internal and external examinations. The annual junior secondary school certificate examination (JSCCE) released by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) justifies the notion that there is poor academic achievement of students in the subject. This poor performance of students is blamed on three major factors: teaching problems/method, negative attitudes of students to the subject, and examination difficulty. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine the effect of Guided discovery teaching method on Basic science students' achievement in secondary schools in Delta North senatorial district.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the effect of guided discovery teaching method on Basic Science students' achievement in secondary schools in Delta North senatorial district.

Specifically, the study sought to:

- to find out if there is a difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic science using guided discovery and lecture method;
- find out if there is an effect of interaction of instructional method and sex on Basic Science students' achievement.

Research questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

- What is the difference in mean achievement score of Basic science students taught using guided discovery method and lecture method?
- What is the effect of interaction of method and sex on Basic Science students' achievement?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated to be tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between mean achievement score of Basic science students taught using guided discovery method and lecture method.
- ii. There is no significant interaction effect of method and sex on Basic Science students' achievement.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test and non-randomized group design. Non – randomized intact classes were assigned to the two teaching methods (independent variables) under consideration. The experimental group (guided discovery) and the control group (lecture method) was employed. The treatment and control groups were taken from four schools in Delta North senatorial district. The total population of JS2 students under study in Delta North senatorial district in the 2023/2024 academic session is six thousand, eight hundred and two (6,802) (Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Board, Asaba, 2024).

Two hundred and twenty-eight (228) JS2 students (107 for experimental group and 121 for control group) constituted the sample for the study. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the four schools and intact classes in Delta North senatorial district. The instrument for data collection is Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) drawn from a six-week instructional unit in Basic Science. The instrument (BSAT), was subjected to face validity by three experts. The reliability of the Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) was established using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (KR_{21}) which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77.

Treatment Procedure

The treatment procedure followed thus:

Step 1: Training of research assistants for 6 days.

Step 2: Pretesting.

Step 3: Actual treatment: After pre-testing, the various methods were used to teach the two groups (Experimental and Control) for 6 weeks.

Step 4: Post-testing: At the end of 6 weeks, the students were post tested using same instrument.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analysed using the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Hypotheses 1 was tested with independent t-test statistics, while hypotheses 2 was tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference in mean achievement score of Basic science students taught using guided discovery method and lecture method?

In answering research question 1, mean and standard deviation statistics was used and the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught with Guide Discovery and those taught with Lecture Teaching Methods

Group	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Std. Deviation
Discovery Method	107	57.06	22.81	9.39
Lecture method	121	34.25		6.95

Table 1 shows a post-test mean achievement score of 57.06, with a standard deviation of 9.39 for the students taught with guided discovery method, while their counterpart taught using lecture method had a post-test mean achievement score of 34.25, with a standard deviation of 6.95. The mean difference between both methods is 22.81, in favour of students taught Basic Science using guided discovery method.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement score of Basic science students taught using guided discovery method and lecture method.

In testing hypothesis 1, t-test analysis was employed and the result is presented in Table 2. To determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{01} , independent t-test statistics was used to analyse the students' scores at pretest.

Table 2: T-test comparison for the equivalent of the groups

Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Guided Discovery	107	28.82	6.324	266	0.44	.965	Not Significant
Lecture Method	121	28.86	6.264				

Table 2 shows that the difference at pre-test is not significance since the calculated Sig value of 0.965 which is greater than 0.05 alpha level of significance was obtained. With this, independent sample t-test statistics becomes the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{01} , as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: T-test comparison of mean achievement post-test scores of students taught Basic Science using guided discovery and lecture method

Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Guided Discovery	107	57.06	6.95	226	21.00	.000	Significant
Lecture Method	121	34.25	9.39				

Table 3 shows that the calculated t-value = 21.00 with p-value of $.000 < 0.05$ alpha level. Since the p-value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis one was rejected. This implies that there is a statistically significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught using guided discovery method and lecture method, in favour of students taught Basic Science using guided discovery method.

Research Question 2

What is the effect of interaction of method and sex on Basic Science students' achievement?
In answering research question 2, mean and standard deviation statistics was employed and the result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the Interaction Effect of Instructional Method and Sex on Students' Achievement

Teaching Method	Sex	N	\bar{X}	\bar{X} Df	SD
Guided Discovery		107	57.06		6.95
				22.81	
Lecture Method		121	34.25		9.39
Guided Discovery	Male	48	57.52	0.84	9.85
	Female	59	56.68		9.06
Lecture Method	Male	48	29.37	0.85	6.45
	Female	73	28.52		6.25

Table 4 shows a post-test mean achievement score of 57.06 and 34.25 for Guided discovery and Lecture method respectively; then a post-test Mean achievement score of 57.52 and 56.68, for male and female students taught Basic Science with guided discovery (experimental group) while male and female students taught Basic Science with lecture method had a Mean achievement score of 29.37 and 28.52. The results do not suggest interaction effect of instructional method and sex on students' achievement in Basic Science, since the mean difference of both methods and sexes were computed at 0.84 and 0.85 respectively, which is not significant.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant interaction effect of method and sex on Basic Science students' achievement.

In testing hypothesis 2, Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed and result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) showing the effect of interaction between instructional method and sex on students' Basic Science achievement

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	53632.668 ^a	4	13408.167	528.422	.000
Intercept	1867.890	1	1867.890	73.614	.000
Pretest	8445.932	1	8445.932	332.858	.000
Sex	45.563	1	45.563	1.796	.182
Method	52239.924	1	52239.924	2058.799	.000
Sex * Method	.175	1	.175	.007	.934
Error	5658.397	223	25.374		
Total	463249.000	228			
Corrected Total	59291.066	227			

- i. R Squared = .905 (Adjusted R Squared = .903)
- ii. Computed using alpha = .05

Table 5 shows that the computed value of $F = .007$; p -value $0.934 > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant interaction effect of method and sex on Basic science students' achievement is not rejected. Hence, there is no statistically significant effect of interaction of instructional method and sex on students' achievement in Basic Science.

Discussion of Results

The first finding shows that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Basic Science students taught using Guided discovery and Lecture methods. The results revealed that students exposed to guided discovery method performed significantly better in Basic Science compared to those who received lecture teaching method. This is an indication that students taught with guided discovery method performed significantly better than those taught with lecture method. This agrees with the report of Akpotu (2017), who conducted a study titled "The effect of guided discovery teaching method on junior secondary school students' achievement in Basic Science".

This finding also concurs with Adekunle (2015) who reported that students taught using guided discovery and think-pair-share techniques got a higher posttest mean score compared to the lecture method. He also found that these two techniques had a high potential for enhancing students' achievement in Chemistry and Science learning. Also, Olorode and Jimoh (2016) in their study reported that guided discovery teaching method is more efficient than lecture teaching method in the learning of financial accounting in Colleges of Education in Ogun State. Similarly, Adeoye and Oladipo (2015) conducted a study titled "Influence of guided discovery teaching method on secondary school students' achievement in Basic Science". They found that students in the experimental group, who were taught using the guided discovery teaching method, scored significantly higher on achievement tests in Basic Science compared to students in the control group. This also suggests that the guided discovery teaching method had a positive influence on students' achievement in Basic Science. Furthermore, in research carried out by Salihu (2015) shows that students taught with guided discovery method performed better than those with lecture

method. This suggests that the guided discovery teaching method had a positive effect on students' achievement in Basic Science.

The second finding revealed that there no significant interaction effect between instructional methods and sex on students' achievement in Basic Science. This implies that students' achievement in Basic Science relative to instructional method is not influenced by students' sex. This finding is in agreement with that of Owo, Idode and Ikwut (2016) who revealed a no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on students' academic achievement in Chemistry. This is also similar to Suleiman (2010) and Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013) findings in related studies where they found out that gender had no significant interaction between the treatment and gender on the performance of students in mathematics. This finding also collaborates with Imoniwhe (2023) who found that there is no significant effect of interaction between sex and teaching method as measured by students' mean retention scores in Chemistry. However, the finding disagreed with that of Adeyemi and Ajibade (2011) who revealed that there was significant interaction effect on instructional method and gender on students' achievement in Social Studies.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that: Guided discovery method improves students' achievement in Basic Science more than lecture method. There is no statistically significant interaction effect of instructional method and sex on students' achievement in Basic science.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study and the conclusion drawn, it is recommended that:

1. Educational authorities and school administrators should integrate the guided discovery teaching method into the Basic Science curriculum, ensuring that teachers are trained to effectively utilize this approach to enhance students learning outcome.
2. Government should invest in appropriate teaching resources such as laboratory equipment, teaching aids, and technology that facilitate the implementation of guided discovery activities, allowing for a hands-on learning experience.
3. Basic science teachers should use more of Guided discovery strategies such as questioning, collaboration, exploration and meaningful charts.

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